

NOTES ON PHOTO-MONTAGE

The philosophical twist to be added (to parallax), of course, is that the observed distance is not simply subjective, since the same object that exists “out there” is seen from two different stances, or points of view. It is rather that, as Hegel would have put it, subject and object are inherently mediated so that an “epistemological” shift in the subject’s point of view always reflects an ontological shift in the object itself. Or – to put it in Lacanese – the subject’s gaze is always-already inscribed into the perceived object itself, in the guise of its “blind spot,” that which is “in the object more than object itself,” the point from which the object itself returns the gaze. Sure, the picture is in my eye, but I am also in the picture.¹ – Slavoj Žižek

Paolo Veronese, *The Wedding at Cana* (1562-1563).

The photo-montaged images take still images from photo-reconnaissance conducted at the Palladian Refectory, in August 2021, add a vertical black line to emphasize precise orthographic orientation, and superimpose them onto an image of *The Wedding at Cana*. The black line also serves as a type of mnemonic device (totem) signaling subjective imposition into the field of the photograph and, via montage, the resulting subject-object dialogue.

To further trouble mere orthographic perspectival concerns and the conceptual mysteries of parallax, as examined through the photo-reconnaissance (using the human figure for scale and in relation to the hypothetically contiguous perspectival lines of “room and painting” conjoined as “theater”), the photographic image

¹ Slavoj Žižek, *The Parallax View* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2006), p. 17.

and its black field (derived from PDF) are rotated in space (via PPT) and/or the photographic image and black field plus the image of the painting are rotated in space to destabilize conventional orientation and introduce opportunities for accidental or incidental instances of Romantic subjective-idealist (“Fichtean”) anamorphosis to occur, *via embedded symmetry*, further destabilizing conventional viewing of “photograph and painting,” as montaged affective artifact.

Notably, the montage also brings the painting into the room, through the window/frame of the superimposed photographic image made transparent (50%). See Figure 3, in particular, for this haunting through doubling of affect. In turning the photographic image and black field plus painting (as singularity) into a preliminary two-dimensional plane, receding in space, the vertical and horizontal lines of the architectural mise-en-scène are transposed to a liminality that sets in motion a form of presentism given to the agency of the interpretive reading.

Paolo Veronese, *Agony in the Garden* (1583-84).

See also, “Veronese,” Gavin Keeney, w/ Andreas Philippopoulos-Mihalopoulos, Chiara Casarin, Ilenia Maschietto, and Neža Zajc, *Vesper: Journal of Architecture, Arts & Theory* 8: Vesper (Spring-Summer 2023)

https://www.iuav.it/sites/default/files/2024-11/Vesper%20No.%208_Vesper_WEB_20_Keeney%2C%20Philippopoulos-Mihalopoulos.pdf

FIGURES 1-9 – Photos by Ilenia Maschietto and Chiara Casarin, PDF of photos with black line and black field by Owen O’Carroll, photo-montage via PPT by Gavin Keeney.

